

Transition Metal Complexes of Cinnamoylhydrazine

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Manuscript received 5 March 1979, accepted 29 December 1979

Cinnamoylhydrazine (CH) form complexes with Co(II), Ni(II), Mn(II), Fe(III), Cr(III), Zn(II), Cd(II), and Hg(II). Their structures have been proposed on the basis of analytical, conductance and infrared data. Hg(II), Cd(II), Mn(II) and Zn(II) complexes coordinate via carbonyl oxygen and NH₂ groups, while Co(II), Ni(II), Fe(III) and Cr(III) complexes coordinate through the imidol structure. Spectral data confirm the tetrahedral structure for cobalt chloride and bromide, a square planar structure for Ni and an octahedral structure for Cr.

OUR earlier work¹⁻⁵ on the complexes of hydrazide has been extended to the complexes of cinnamoylhydrazine (C₉H₉.CH=CH.CONHNH₂) with some transition metal ions. In this paper we report the preparation and characterization of Co(II), Ni(II), Fe(III), Cr(III), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes of cinnamoylhydrazine.

Experimental

Materials and Methods :

All the chemicals were of AR or C.P grades. Cinnamoylhydrazine was prepared by the method described in the literature⁶.

Preparation of the Complexes :

1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 M:L complexes were prepared by refluxing equimolar amounts of CH and the metal salts in ethanolic solution. The precipitation of the complexes was aided by digestion on a water bath for about one hour. The resulting precipitate was filtered, washed with hot ethanol and then dried in a desiccator over anhydrous calcium chloride.

Analysis :

The analyses for the metals and halides were carried out by the standard methods⁷⁻⁸. Hydrazine was estimated volumetrically by Jalmesons method⁹. Carbon and hydrogen analysis were performed by the Micro-analytical Unit at the University of Cairo. The analytical data are given in Table 1.

Physical Measurements :

IR spectra (4000-625 cm⁻¹) were recorded on a Pye Unicam SP. 2000 Spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Pye Unicam SP. 1800 Spectrophotometer. Molar conductance measurements were carried out on Tacussel conductivity bridge type CD 6 NG with cell constant 0.97 cm⁻¹ in DMF at concentration 10⁻³ M.

Results and Discussion

The bonding sites in cinnamoylhydrazine complexes have been established by a comparison of their infrared spectra with that of the parent ligand.

Cinnamoylhydrazine reacts with Mn(II), Cd(II), Zn(II) and Hg(II) salts (I-XI) in the keto form as shown by the presistance of amide II band in the spectra of the complexes. The amide I band was shifted to a lower frequency by $\approx 10-20$ cm⁻¹. Similar behaviour has been reported earlier for metal (II)-semicarbazide¹⁰, semicarbazone¹⁰ and some substituted benzylidene aroylhydrazine¹¹. Also, the NH₂ bending vibration band is shifted to a lower frequency by $\approx 20-30$ cm⁻¹. In these metal chelates the ligand being bidentate coordinate via NH₂ and C=O groups.

In the spectra of the complexes (XII to XVIII), amide I band at 1680 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of the ligand was displaced in the complexes. The amide II band at 1555 cm⁻¹ disappeared and a strong band at 1530 cm⁻¹ appeared. This may be attributed to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ ¹² formed as a result of enolization of the hydrogen of NH group to its adjacent carbonyl. In the spectra of these complexes a $\nu(\text{-C-O-})$ ¹³ was observed at 1070 cm⁻¹ together with an OH bending frequency at ≈ 1200 cm⁻¹ which indicate that the ligand has been reacted in the imidol structure.

Electronic Spectra :

The electronic spectra of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cr(III) complexes are reported in Table 2. The absorption spectra in DMF are similar to those in mujol mull indicating that their no difference in stereochemistry between the solid and the solution.

Visible spectra of the complexes XII, XIII and XIV show two bands in the range 16181-16234 and 14663 cm⁻¹ indicating thus tetrahedral complexes for Co(II)^{4,15}. Ni complexes (XV and XVI) show only one band in the region 22222-16667 cm⁻¹ suggesting

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

No.	Compound	M.P.	Colour	% Calculated					% Found					Molar conductance in DMF
				C	H	Cl or Br	Metal	N ₂ H ₄	C	H	Cl or Br	Metal	N ₂ H ₄	
	CH	101	Yellowish-white	66.64	6.21	—	—	19.76	66.41	6.13	—	—	19.70	—
I	Hg(CH)Cl ₂ .H ₂ O	>260	dirty white	23.93	2.68	15.70	44.41	7.09	23.30	2.40	15.57	44.66	6.54	13.5
II	Zn(CH)Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	>260	white	32.31	4.22	21.19	19.68	9.60	31.90	4.00	21.13	20.20	10.08	16.5
III	Zn(CH) ₂ Cl ₂	>260	„	52.06	4.85	11.38	10.57	12.20	52.60	4.60	10.70	9.90	12.60	130.00
IV	Zn(CH)Br ₂ .2H ₂ O	>260	„	25.49	3.33	37.71	15.42	7.50	24.40	3.70	37.03	15.63	6.61	18.5
V	Zn(CH) ₂ .Br ₂	>260	yellow	39.34	3.67	29.09	11.88	11.60	39.10	3.30	30.12	9.63	10.19	26.10
VI	Cd(CH)Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	>260	white	28.33	3.70	18.58	29.64	8.40	28.10	3.80	18.65	28.80	9.20	20.20
VII	Cd(CH) ₂ Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	>260	„	45.95	4.85	10.02	15.87	13.50	46.20	5.00	9.60	15.45	12.93	140.30
VIII	Cd(CH)Br ₂	>260	pale yellow	24.88	2.32	36.79	25.87	7.30	24.40	2.00	36.07	25.93	8.80	18.90
IX	Cd(CH) ₂ Br ₂	>260	„ „	36.24	3.38	26.80	18.84	10.70	36.30	23.00	26.01	19.23	9.39	22.40
X	Mn(CH)Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	210	white	33.36	4.35	21.88	16.95	9.89	33.20	4.10	20.20	6.01	10.36	12.50
XI	Mn(CH) ₂ Cl ₂	235	„	48.02	4.48	15.75	12.02	12.45	47.90	4.60	15.30	13.01	13.30	13.50
XII	Co(CH)Cl ₂ .H ₂ O	>260	grey	34.86	3.90	22.87	19.01	10.33	33.70	3.40	22.20	19.60	10.40	21.60
XIII	Co(CH) ₂ Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	>260	rose	44.10	4.93	14.46	12.02	13.02	44.20	4.50	14.26	11.90	13.38	28.90
XIV	Co(CH)Br ₂ .2H ₂ O	>260	„	25.92	3.38	38.32	14.13	7.70	26.60	3.40	38.80	13.91	7.43	23.50
XV	Ni(CH) ₂ Cl ₂ .H ₂ O	>260	dull green	45.80	4.70	15.02	12.43	13.58	45.40	4.30	15.90	12.03	13.40	33.60
XVI	Ni(CH)Cl ₂	>260	„ „	37.04	3.45	24.30	20.10	10.90	37.60	3.70	23.70	21.00	10.64	18.40
XVII	Fe(CH)Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	>260	brown	29.99	3.91	29.51	15.49	8.89	30.20	4.10	29.99	14.69	8.63	20.55
XVIII	Cr(CH)Cl ₂ .5H ₂ O	>260	grey	25.21	4.70	24.81	—	7.05	26.50	4.70	24.72	—	7.32	19.60

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA

Complexes	Soln. ^(a)			Solid	
	cm ⁻¹	nm	ε	cm ⁻¹	nm
1—Co(CH)Cl ₂ .H ₂ O	16181	618	370	16129	620
	14663	682	500	15152	660
2—Co(CH) ₂ Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	16234	616	380	16252	615
	14663	682	515	15385	650
3—Co(CH)Br ₂ .2H ₂ O	—	—	—	16393	610
	—	—	—	15504	645
4—Cr(CH)Cl ₂ .5H ₂ O	—	—	—	17860	560
5—Ni(CH)Cl ₂	—	—	—	16667	600
6—Ni(CH) ₂ Cl ₂ .H ₂ O	—	—	—	17241	580

(a) data obtained in DMF solution.

therefore a square planar configuration^{16,17}. Cr complex (XVIII) show only one band around 17000 cm⁻¹ which is in a good agreement with the values for octahedral Cr(III) complexes reported in the literature¹⁸⁻²⁰.

Conductance Measurements :

The molar conductance values (Λ_m) in DMF at the concentration 10⁻³ M are relatively low and are comparable to those of non-electrolytic solutions. However, two exceptional cases were recorded for Zn(II) and Cd(II) (structure III and VII), where values of 150 and 140.3 ohm⁻¹cm⁻²M⁻¹ have been measured for Zn(II) and Cd(II) respectively high values indicate the occurrence of two chlorine ions in DMF.

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